

UDK 624.011.1(07)**ASSESSMENT OF EARTHQUAKE RESISTANCE OF WOODEN
BUILDINGS**

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Annotatio. Wood-frame buildings are very common inregions that are exposed to earthquakes. Most of residentialbuildings are constructed usingthis technology; therefore, the seismicresistance of them is really essentialin order to prevent human losses and structural damage. The aim of the present articleis to show the results of the detailednumerical FEM analysis focused on the seismicbehaviour of the wood-frame house withdifferentin-wall insulationmaterials. The results of the study clearly indicate that using polyurethane (PU) foam instead of mineral wool leads to the increasein the rigidity of the structure and, therefore, to the substantialreductionin the structural response under differentseismicexcitations.

Keywords: wood-frame buildings, seismicresistance, thermal insulation, PU foam.

INTRODUCTION

A lot of structures suffer from damage during major earthquakes as the

result of dangerous seismic loads [1–4]. Buildings of high importance, e.g. hospitals, fire departments, crisis management centres are designed in accordance with standards that included different aspects of earthquake risks and adequate preventive measures. Methods of strengthening those structures, mainly build of reinforced concrete and steel frames, are subjected to many studies, including experimental and numerical ones. On the other hand, wood-frame buildings, due to rather low erection cost and their function related mostly to residential housing needs, have not been analysed so intensively.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Apart from other different methods of strengthening of wood-frame buildings, the influence of in-wall insulation has not been study so far from the point of view of seismic resistance. The authors conducted a series of tests and analyses using polyurethane (PU) foam as in-wall insulation and comparing it with the traditional insulation consisting of mineral wool. Some previous results have already been published, including the results from the experimental tests on simple frame element [2] and the preliminary results of modal analysis for simplified numerical structural model [3]. The aim of the present article is to show the results of the detailed numerical analysis focused on the seismic behaviour of the wood-frame house insulated with PU foam, as compared to the structural behaviour when mineral wool is used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The numerical analysis was carried out using the commercial FEM software Dlubal RFEM. For the purpose of the analysis, a 3D model of a typical single-storey wood-frame house was created, as shown in Fig. 1. The length and width of the building are equal to 12.0 m and 12.0 m, respectively. The ground floor height is equal to 2.80 m, while the total height is 6.35 m.

Fig.13 3D numerical model of a typical wood-frame house

The walls of the numerical model were created from a number of composite structural elements (see Fig. 2) consisting of four types of shell elements – one representing the wood frame and three representing three layers (two external simulating OSB sheathing and an internal one simulating mineral wool or PU foam). These three layers were fully connected one to another in the case of the panel with PU foam representing the situation when the PU foam is injected inside OSB sheathing and it bonds wood elements together. On the other hand, a lack of such a connection between the three layers was assumed in the numerical model when mineral wool is used, so as to simulate the situation when mineral wool is only inserted inside OSB sheathing. It should be underlined that such composite elements represent directly the experimental models of typical wall members in a wood-frame building.

Fig.2 Composite element with visible 3 layers of shell elements representing OSB sheathing and thermal insulation

In the first part of the numerical analysis, the modal analysis has been conducted and the general characteristics (eigenfrequencies and vibration modes) of the building insulated with mineral wool and PU foam have been obtained. The results of the analysis in the form of the first three vibration modes are shown in Figs. 3–4.

Fig.3 1st eigenform for the building with mineral wool ($f_1=1.890\text{Hz}$)

Fig.4nd eigenform for the building with mineral wool ($f_2=1.975\text{Hz}$)

The time step of each analysis was identical as the time step of the recorded accelerogram, i.e. 0.01 s for the Tabas and Athens earthquakes, 0.02 s for the Northridge and Loma Prieta earthquakes. The two ends of the opposite roof eaves as well as both endpoint of the roof (see Fig.5) were used as reference nodes so as to compare the results for both numerical models of the building.

Fig.5 View of the 3D model from the top showing the reference nodes

CONCLUSION

The behaviour of a typical residential wood-frame building with different in-wall insulation materials has been numerically studied under different earthquake excitations. A modal analysis has been first performed to estimate the dynamic characteristics of the model created. Then, the time history seismic analyses have been conducted and the structural responses of the building insulated with mineral wool and PU foam have been compared. The results of the study clearly indicate that using PU foam instead of mineral wool for the in-wall insulation of a wood-frame building leads to the increase in the rigidity of the structure.

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